

The influence of internal marketing on employees' organizational commitment: evidence from small and medium retailing enterprises in Zimbabwe

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This study aims to establish the influence of internal marketing on employees' organizational commitment towards the small and medium retailing enterprise sector in Zimbabwe. The social exchange theory and the side-bet theory anchored the theoretical foundation of this study. A drop and pick-up survey strategy was used to collect data from retailing personnel. An undisguised structured questionnaire was administered to selected participants and had question items on demographics, internal marketing (rewards, training, internal communication, and empowerment), and organizational commitment. The results indicate that internal marketing variables influence the organizational commitment of SME retail employees. Implications for managers are that proper implementation of internal marketing strategies by retail SME managers can result in higher levels of employee organizational commitment, vital for organizational competitiveness.

Keywords: Marketing, Internal marketing, commitment, organizational commitment, retailing SMEs

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Introduction

The concept of internal marketing is premised on the understanding that organizations are obliged to consider employees as valuable and critical assets for the success of their operations (Longbottom et al. 2006). Internal marketing is, therefore, a vital tool for attracting, developing, motivating, and retaining high-caliber staff, which are vital for building sustainable competitive advantage (Jevanovic et al. 2023). Since organizations operate in highly dynamic and competitive environments, gaining competitive advantage has become the priority, and this can be achieved by developing highly committed employees who identify with an organization and unilaterally accept an organization's objectives as portraying their interests (Cassim et al. 2024). When employees show more commitment to the organization, it increases its competitiveness. Highly committed employees are self-directed, enjoy job satisfaction, have greater

desires for job performance, are least desirous of leaving the organization, identify with organizational goals and ideals, and develop organizational citizenship behaviors (Cassim et al. 2024). Internal marketing is, therefore, the fulcrum for enhancing job satisfaction and ultimate organizational commitment (Jovanović et al. 2023). Extant research confirmed that organizational commitment is an antecedent to organizational performance (Mero et al. 2020). Highly committed employees are prepared to serve an organization throughout their productive work lives and exhibit good citizenship behaviors towards the organization. Organizations ought to create holistic marketing-based orientations to encourage employees to assimilate the organization's mission and vision and embrace favorable customer-oriented behaviors. In this regard, internal marketing motivates employees to remain focused to achieve defined organizational goals. Organizations today face challenges in trying to build employee commitment. Commitment entails the propensity of an employee to identify with and contribute to a particular organization (Ramos 2015). As alluded to by Cassim et al. (2024), when employees are committed, become advocates, and adhere to the company's goals, they become more dedicated and less eager to look for other employment opportunities. Organizational commitment refers to employees' attitudinal predispositions toward the organizations they work for (Zangene-Tabar et al. 2013). Meyer and Allen (1997) opined that organizational commitment is a multifaceted dimension that is categorized into affective, continuance, and normative commitment. Affective commitment unconditionally influences employees to develop an emotional attachment, identify with a particular organization, and are keen to achieve their goals together with the organization. Continuance commitment is premised on the understanding that employees are less effective but continue to work for the organization in fear of what becomes of them after leaving the job. Normative commitment is based on norms and values where employees succumb to socialization pressure from other employees. In this case, employees feel obliged to remain loyal to the organization. Normative commitment generally results from internalizing normative pressures before or after joining the organization. The absence of internal marketing negatively affects employees' organizational commitment, and this negatively affects organizational performance. Although several studies have been conducted on internal marketing and its impact on organizational commitment (Caruana & Calleya 1998, Thanh 2018), little has been done to establish the impact of internal marketing on employee organizational commitment in the retailing sector. There is no apparent evidence in the literature that supports the effect internal marketing bears on employee organizational commitment in the small and medium retailing enterprise sector in Africa, particularly Zimbabwe, resulting in a research gap that this study aims to fill. As such Zimbabwe business environment is unique due to its international relations.

This study investigates to interrogate the influence of internal marketing dimensions on employees' organizational commitment in Zimbabwe. The first part of this study proffers a prologue that describes the basic building blocks of the association between internal marketing and organizational commitment in retailing SMEs. After that, the ensuing section dwells on the review of supporting extant literature. Literature on SMEs, supporting theories, and the nexus between IM and OC is expounded in this regard. The review establishes the extent of research coverage in the retailing sector and envisages the gap and niche the current study can fill in. Subsequently, it presents the philosophy, approach, methods, and tools used in this study, followed by analysis, discussion of results, study implications and conclusions.

Literature Review

Small and Medium Retailing Enterprises

According to Makanyeza et al. (2023), "small and medium enterprises (SMEs) play an essential role in economic growth and sustainable development worldwide." In line with Rungani and Potgieter (2018), the trio affirm that SMEs' significant contributions include employment creation, social development, gross domestic product, and income generation. As reiterated by Gomwe et al. (2023), Nodira and Rashid (2022)

claim that the developing economies particularly in Africa recognize the strategic relevance of small, medium and micro organizations as mainstay stakeholders of a country's economy. The term SME has no single globally acknowledged definition (Albalushi & Naqshbandi 2022). It should be noted that every approach defines what constitutes a small organization. In the United States of America (USA), the Small Business Administration (SBA) defines a small business as employing less than 500 employees. An array of definitions has been used to describe small and medium enterprises; however, researchers adopted the Wiltshire Committee's definition, which states that an SME "is a business in which one or two persons are required to make all the important management decisions such as finance, accounting, personnel, purchasing, processing or servicing, marketing, selling, without the aid of internal specialists and with specific knowledge in only one or two functional areas." The European Commission distinguishes SME categories, i.e. micro, small, and medium enterprises, on the basis of size criteria such as employee establishment, annual income, and annual balance sheet total. However, the definition has been reviewed to align with economic changes in the following manner: (1) Micro: below ten employees, with an annual income of £2 million; (2) Small: 50 employees and yearly earnings of £10 million, and (3) Medium: with an establishment 250 employees and yearly earnings of £50 million. From a retailing perspective, the UK also categorizes SMEs using a three-pronged approach; wherein retail organizations use employee numbers, number of outlets, and volume of sales. Between 10 and 100 employees are for medium retail businesses, while small retailers employ ten employees or fewer. The second approach to defining retailing SMEs focuses on the number of outlets, i.e., single and chain stores. The last approach to defining retailing SMEs is based on sales volume. Studying the link between internal marketing (i.e. training, rewards, internal communication, and employee empowerment) and organizational commitment in the retailing SME sector brings a new dimension to research, as no such studies have been commissioned in Zimbabwe, let alone in the African context that focused on retailing SMEs. The internal marketing has been deemed this sector's most befitting element.

Theoretical Framework

The Social Exchange Theory (SET)

SET remains one of the most popular and influential business and social sciences theories. Ahmad et al. (2023) state that SET is "one of the gold standards to understand workplace behavior, which has the potential to provide a unitary framework for much of organizational behavior." Researchers from numerous disciplines acknowledge this theory's significance in describing human interactions in many settings, of which the workplace is not an exception (Tripp 2023). The theory is premised on the conviction that individuals create and maintain social relationships, hoping that those relations will bear mutually beneficial outcomes, contingent on evaluating the association's particular costs and benefits. SET is a classic theory emphasizing that individuals acquire resources and benefits through exchange and create mutual relationships.

The SET theory states that human societies thrive through interactions and communication. The theory affirms that exchanges are not restricted to material resources but also encompass emotional, informational, and power exchanges and other valuable aspects. Thus, in this regard, employees, particularly those in the small and medium retailing sector, ought to consider their own desires and gains and those of their employers to realize positive interaction and cooperation. Internal marketing is a significant driver of social exchange. Thus, internal marketing aims to create conditions that satisfy the needs of an organization's employees. If such conditions are met, and internal solid bonds are formed. In that case, employees feel satisfied and are indebted to reciprocate to the organization by demonstrating positive job attitudes and behavior, such as trust, job satisfaction, and commitment.

The Side-Bet Theory

The "side-bet" theory is a pre-eminent commitment theory propounded by Becker in 1960. It stresses that employees are devoted to the organizations they work for due to the hidden investment they have in the organization, the *side bet*. Georges (2020) affirmed that certain costs accumulate over time, making it problematic for employees to divorce themselves from a routinized pattern of activity to maintain affiliation with the organization. Becker (1960) opined that the procedures employees follow in committing themselves to the organization are the *side-bets*, and these invest effort, time and reward. As Moeng et al. (2023) alluded to, such investments are the sources of cost that impede, to some extent, employee's independence in their future activity. Employees endure captive loyalty due to the costs associated with their decisions to leave the organization. According to Moeng et al. (2023), "Becker's Side Bet theory is grounded in the principle that commitment is a disposition to be attached to the organization as a result of the accumulation of *side bets* that would be lost if the employment is terminated". In the context of the retail small and medium enterprises sector, employees develop continuance commitment due to the fear of losing their investments in their organizations.

Internal Marketing

Internal marketing (IM) has been variously defined. Ismail and Sheriff (2017) claim that researchers have not agreed on a particular definition for the past three and a half decades. Rafiq and Ahmed (2000) describe IM as "a planned effort using a marketing-like-approach to overcome organizational resistance to change and to align, motivate and inter-functionally coordinate and integrate employees towards the effective implementation of corporate and functional strategies in order to deliver customer satisfaction through a process of creating motivated and customer orientated employees." Longbottom et al. (2006) suggest, "Internal marketing is a philosophy that treats employees as internal customers and their jobs as products which are supposed to satisfy their needs." Internal marketing seeks to satisfy the needs of employees since this translates to satisfying the needs of external customers. Naturally, satisfied employees are highly motivated and eager to remain loyal to the organization, enhancing external customer satisfaction.

Organizational Commitment

The term organizational commitment has been defined in different but related ways. Organizational commitment occurs when an employee identifies with an organization and is willing to work for it. Or Accordingly, Sigit and Muafi (2022) posit that, "organizational commitment is the psychological view of organizational members towards their attachment to the organization where they work." It is a vital determinant that measures whether employees will remain committed to working for the organization for a prolonged time period with the desire to achieve organizational goals. Organizational commitment is deemed an attitudinal or behavioral predisposition that aligns an employee to an organization and depresses them from shifting from the current workplace. Organizational commitment measures the scope employees are devoted to helping the organization realize its goals while personally identifying and involving themselves with the organization. It is manifested through employee behaviors, beliefs, and attitudes and can be measured on a continuum. Meyer and Allen (1997) developed a three-dimensional model of organizational commitment; namely, affective, continuance, and normative commitment. The former develops when individual employees unconditionally subscribe to an organization's mission, vision, goals, and moral values. Employees develop emotional attachments to their organizations to the extent that they feel that their organizations' successes lie with them. Research has shown that affective commitment results in higher employee performance, favorable work attitude, and willingness to spend an entire productive work life with the same organization.

Employees are often calculative when entering into a relationship with an organization. Continuance commitment entails individuals considering their association with the organization based on what they

benefit in exchange for the effort expended and what is likely to be lost upon leaving the job (i.e. remuneration, benefits, and relations). In this case, employees are only prepared to do their best when they perceive that the rewards they receive meet or exceed their expectations. To an extent, continuance commitment is achieved due to the desire of an individual employee to satisfy their own needs (Lewicka et al. 2017). Employees endure captive loyalty to an organization because of their fear of anticipated costs. In certain circumstances, employees remain working for specific organizations because of their situations (e.g. family challenges, health conditions, professional caliber, racial and cultural backgrounds). Normative commitment develops when an employee remains loyal to an organization because it conforms to their standards of behavior and moral values. Employees in this category are obedient, cautious, and prefer to formalize issues. These tend to portray similar attitudinal and behavioral characteristics to employees with affective commitment. Normative commitment is influenced by norms and values that govern the extent of loyalty, sense of compulsion, and allegiance to the organization (Lewicka et al. 2017). Thus, normative commitment is an ethically driven motive to remain in the organization.

Internal Marketing and Organizational Commitment

Internal marketing is based on the conviction that management's mandate is to provide need-satisfying attributes to its employees, leading to job contentment and organizational commitment (Ismail & Sheriff 2017). Productivity and reduced employee turnover are benefits associated with internal marketing. In their study of retail banking, Caruana and Calleya (1998) discovered that internal marketing is positively correlated with affective commitment. Highly committed employees are prepared to render high-quality services and to remain working for the organization. In Vietnam, a study in the SME services sector by Thanh (2018) found that internal marketing (IM) constructs, such as leadership, working environment, person-organization fit, and pay satisfaction, are positively correlated to affective, continuance, and normative commitment. Evidently, prior studies have examined internal marketing as a determinant of commitment and confirmed that it exerts a positive effect. Ismail and Sheriff (2017) focused on internal marketing constructs such as managerial support, empowerment, empathy, staff appraisals, and reward systems, and their results affirmed that internal marketing is a predictor of organizational commitment.

Conceptual Framework

Based on the evidence enshrined in the literature, the conceptual framework depicting the association between the independent and dependent variables in terms of their constructs is reflected in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The Conceptual Framework

Source: the authors

Hypotheses Development

The ensuing hypotheses were proposed in relation to the conceptual framework and empirical evidence from reviewed literature on the link between marketing and employee organizational commitment.

Employee Reward and Organizational Commitment

Studies have established a causative link between an organization's reward systems and organizational commitment. Stanfast and Stanfast (2023) surveyed the impact of rewards (intrinsic and extrinsic) on deposit money bank employees in Nigeria. They established that rewards positively influenced organizational commitment's three constructs— affective, continuance, and normative commitment. Orajaka (2021) also studied the reward of management practices on employee retention and variable payment in South East Nigeria's public institutions. His results confirmed that variable pay positively influenced employee retention, vital for job performance. In their study in Indonesia, Surya et al. (2024) on work performance, organizational commitments and reward systems on job satisfaction it was revealed that rewards had no direct effect on job satisfaction, while the same (extrinsic and intrinsic rewards) directly impacted both performance and commitment. In Malaysia, Pee et al. (2022) explored the nexus between rewards (intrinsic and extrinsic) and employee commitment in the SME sector. They reveal that intrinsic and extrinsic rewards were significant determinants and positively influenced organizational commitment. Generally, studies have revealed rewards influence the extent of employee commitment, but all the prior discussed did not specifically study the relationship between rewards and the affective component (except for Standfast & Stanfast 2023) of organizational commitment; hence, this study hypothesize that:

H1. Rewards significantly influence employees' affective commitment.

Employee Training and Organizational Commitment

Training is critical in any organization as it benefits employees and the organization. According to Nansamba et al. (2024), employee training encompasses all the learning activities that an organization carries to develop employees' knowledge and practical abilities. Training is executed upon employees to enhance their worth and enable them to achieve their tasks effectively. Various studies have been pursued on the association between employee training and organizational commitment. In India, Houlding and Riaz (2022) held a survey of the association between training offered by the Hyderabad Bank and the resultant organizational commitment of employees, and the findings showed that affective and normative commitment were significantly predicted by training during the continuance component heavily dependent on the promotion and salary increment. In a related study, Ametepe et al. (2024) established that employee training and participation significantly positively impacted organizational commitment. On the other hand, ostracism reflected a negative association with organizational commitment among the bank staff. In Pakistan, Hussain et al. (2020) explored the impact of training and development on the organizational commitment of university staff. They confirmed that training and development improved employee knowledge, skills, and abilities, transformed their attitudes and behaviors, and made them develop an emotional attachment to the organization and, as a result, increased their organizational commitment. Based on the discussions, we hypothesize that:

H2. Employee training has a significant favorable influence on the affective commitment of employees.

Internal Communications Training and Organizational Commitment

Internal communication is premised on exchanging information amongst members of an organization in the workplace (Nguyen & Ha 2023). It is used in all organizations to help management interact with employees. In Srilanka, Surangi and Bandara (2022) explored the impact of four internal marketing dimensions (ie employee empowerment, internal communication, rewards, and training and development) on the commitment of executives in the shipbuilding industry. The results showed that all the internal marketing constructs influenced the organizational commitment of employees positively in that sector. According to Mmutle (2021), the relationship between internal communication and employee engagement has not been extensively empirically tested, and as such, the former should be realized as a determinant of the later. Thus, if internal communication is effectively applied, organizations can build and nurture high levels of employee engagement, which are key to enhancing higher performance. Similarly, internal communication can be an antecedent of organizational commitment. As evidenced in the preceding discussion, there is little evidence that points to the relationship between internal communication and employee organizational commitment. So we hypothesize that:

H3. Internal communication positively influences normative commitment.

Employee Empowerment and Organizational Commitment

Employees who are perceived to be empowered and treated well by their employer can become committed and keen to perform their duties well. Employee empowerment, coupled with the mediating role of job satisfaction, influences employee commitment. A related study by Murray and Holmes (2021) in the Canadian hospitality sector revealed that employee empowerment's meaning dimension significantly influenced affective and continuance commitment. In the context of the Indonesian banks, Suprpto and Widigdo (2021) found that employee empowerment, organizational justice, conflict, and work motivation substantially influenced employee performance. Executives play a significant role in providing empowerment and motivation strategies to promote organizational commitment and loyalty to achieve organizational goals. The study by Kyei-Frimpong et al. (2024) in Ghana's hospitality industry established that employee empowerment strongly influenced the three components of organizational commitment: affective, continuance, and normative. As shown by Ruiz-Palomo et al. (2020), employee empowerment substantially increases organizational commitment. Employee empowerment has become a top priority for managers in many industries since it has been proven that highly empowered employees are more committed and devoted to their organizations. Based on the preceding discussions above, we hypothesize:

H4. Employee empowerment has a positive relationship with continuance commitment.

Methodology

Data Collection

A cross-sectional descriptive research design and a drop-and-pick survey method were used to gather data from respondents. The target population of interest was all the small and medium retailing enterprises personnel in Zimbabwe. A disproportionate stratified chance sampling technique was adopted to select respondents from the various categories of employees in the small and medium retailing sector on the basis of convenience. The sample size of 170 respondents was based on the sample size adopted in a related study on internal marketing and organizational commitment in retail banking by Caruana and Calleya (1998).

Sample Characteristics

Of the 170 questionnaires distributed, 146 were successfully completed and were usable for analysis, yielding a response rate of about 86 percent. The distribution of respondents by gender showed that 65% were females (95 questionnaires), and 35 percent were males (51 questionnaires). Till operators had the highest proportion of participation, contributing 54 percent ($n=79$), with ancillary staff contributing 32 percent ($n=47$). Supervisors who participated were very few, as evidenced by a paltry 14 percent ($n=20$), indicating that their numbers in small and medium retailing organizations are also low. The ages of participants ranged from 24–58 years, with a mean age of about 40 years. The bulk of the respondents were permanently employed, numbering 111 (76%). The balance of 35 (24%) constituted the employees engaged as merchandisers working for other manufacturing organizations but deployed in the city's various small and medium retail establishments.

Operationalization of Variables

The constructs of the internal marketing variable were adapted from Ismail and Sheriff (2017) and Efthymiopoulos and Goula (2024), whereas organizational commitment construct was from Meyer and Allen (1997). Each variable was measured on a 5-pt Likert scale (1=strongly disagree, 5=strongly agree). The demographic data of the respondents were analyzed using basic descriptive statistics. At the same time, the product-moment correlation coefficient was employed to determine whether the proposed relationships between internal marketing (IM) and organizational commitment (OC) variables were supported. Before data collection, the research instrument was pre-tested with a small group of respondents who were not considered in the final selection to validate and establish the instrument's reliability. The Cronbach alpha reliability tests for all the constructs were higher than .70, resulting in the approval of the instrument for use.

This study incorporated four internal marketing dimensions, comprising 26 items. The question items were distributed in the following manner: employee rewards (6 items, Cronbach $\alpha=.89$), training (5 items, Cronbach $\alpha=.93$), internal communication (8 items, Cronbach $\alpha=.87$), and employee empowerment (7 items, Cronbach $\alpha=.89$). The dimensions of the organizational commitment comprised three constructs (23 items); namely, affective (7 items, Cronbach $\alpha=.95$), continuance (8 items, Cronbach $\alpha=.90$, and normative commitment (8 items, Cronbach $\alpha=.94$).

Results

Table 1 shows the regression analysis of four internal marketing constructs as predictors of employees' organizational commitment in the SME retailing sector. Employee rewards ($\beta=.14$, $p=.00$) and Training ($\beta=.32$, $p=.02$) indicate that these internal marketing constructs influence employees' organizational commitment. It is the conviction of the small and medium retailing enterprise sector employees that their levels of organizational commitment emanate from rewards and employee training. The findings echo the results found by Bashir and Long (2015), which all confirm that training has a strong positive correlation with elements of organizational commitment, particularly affective and normative commitments. Bashir and Long (2015) contend that investing in employee training is critical for enhancing organizational commitment amongst employees. They claim that training leads to improved organizational performance, which is the basis for competitive advantage, while organizational commitment is vital for employee retention. Internal communication ($\beta=.15$, $p=.03$) and Employee empowerment ($\beta=.16$, $p=.03$) indicate good predictors of employees' organizational commitment to the SME retailing sector. In this regard, employees' organizational commitment was influenced by organizational initiatives that encouraged participation and involvement of employees in decision-making, as well as giving autonomy to employees over their work. On the other hand, internal communication fosters inter-departmental coordination and

integration among various functional areas, resulting in highly esteemed and motivated employees keen to remain bonded to their organizations for the rest of their productive working lives.

Table 1. Regression Coefficients for the Model

Variables	Beta (β)	P
Rewards	.14	.00
Training & development	.32	.02
Internal Communications	.15	.03
Employee empowerment	.16	.03

Table 2 shows that all the internal marketing variables correlate to employee organizational commitment, with varying significance levels. Employee training and affective commitment show a much higher correlation compared to other associations on internal marketing constructs and organizational commitment. Employee rewards and affective commitment have a moderate correlation, which reflects that rewards are an important antecedent of employee normative commitment. Internal communication is relatively lowly correlated to employee normative commitment. Thus, internal communication's influence on employee normative commitment is mediocre. Employee empowerment also has a positive correlation with continuance commitment. In sum, internal marketing elements positively influence organizational commitment components as evidenced by all significant correlations. Therefore, all hypotheses are supported.

Table 2. Correlations

The link between IM & OC Variables	r	p
Employee rewards versus affective commitment	.53	.00
Employee training versus affective commitment	.73	.04
Internal communications versus normative commitment	.45	.01
Employee empowerment versus continuance commitment	.43	.02

Discussion

Evidence suggests that employee rewards are critical determinants of organizational commitment (Somoye & Eyupoglu 2020). However, the results of this study also indicate a significant correlation between rewards and employee affective commitment. This study, therefore, advocates that although reasonable remuneration and benefits are vital for retailing SME employees, it is noteworthy to consider the significance of other internal marketing elements in eliciting the desired levels of employee commitment in retail SMEs. Employee training strongly correlates with employee affective commitment, which is in sync with the findings of Nansamba et al. (2024). This result buttresses the findings of prior studies, which confirm that when staffs are trained, they become more knowledgeable and can better understand customer expectations today and in the future (Brammah 2016). Thus, staff development generally boosts job performance and significantly influences employee commitment in all organizations, including the retail SME sector.

In an organization, coordination can be achieved if there is effective internal communication between management and employees and among the employees. Internal communication (IC) and normative organizational commitment results revealed a weak positive correlation, corresponding to Mero et al. (2020) findings on the association between internal communications and organizational commitment. This current study's results are unique in that they sought to uncover the link between internal communication and normative commitment, which has not been the case with prior studies that linked internal communication to organizational commitment. This study suggests that small retail and medium

enterprises develop strategies that encourage effective internal communication between managers and employees, as this is essential for inducing organizational commitment. Our results reflect that employee empowerment exerts a positive influence on employee organizational commitment in the SME retail sector. Other studies also affirm that employee empowerment positively influences employee organizational commitment. As alluded to by Braimah (2016), employees that allowed to exercise their discretion and make decisions when dealing with customers develop a great sense of self-efficacy, thereby becoming more devoted to their organizations

The small and medium retailing enterprise sector's overall internal marketing initiatives affect how employees feel contented with their jobs, which ultimately results in employee organizational commitment. Employee rewards are vital in inducing organizational commitment among employees. If employees are rewarded, they become highly motivated and productive. They become selfless and committed to rendering their best service to their employers. If more training is given to this sector, commitment to their organizations will deepen. Training is critical for employees because it enables them to develop a holistic understanding of the organization's mission, vision, and products and services. Employee training helps them fully understand what customers need and what they are supposed to do in relation to others in the organization. "Effective training and development initiatives are necessary to nurture organizational commitment, also known as "the degree to which an individual identifies with and is involved in a given organization" (Nansamba et al. 2024). Internal communication is another indispensable construct of internal marketing critical for enhancing employee organizational commitment. It enhances inter-functional coordination and integration amongst various departments, thereby creating one voice throughout the organization. Open access to information among the members of an organization results in harmonious relationships, which lead to teamwork, motivation, patriotism, productivity, and, ultimately, organizational commitment. A participatory approach to decision-making processes is a key managerial approach to increasing employee affective commitment. Empowerment entails giving employees some platforms to act autonomously and make decisions critical for completing their jobs (Braimah 2016). By exercising their discretion during service delivery and retailing, SME employees create favorable environments that boost their morale and confidence, which is essential for inducing organizational commitment. Employee empowerment gives them the autonomy to make decisions and authority over their work. Decision-making is a vital tool for enhancing employee motivation and organizational commitment. Managers should accept employees' suggestions, opinions, and recommendations as these are of utmost importance to organizational commitment.

Implications for Managers

The outcomes of this study reflect strategic implications for the small and medium retailing sector management and other researchers. All managers in this sector should recognize the validity of internal marketing as the basis for cultivating employee organizational commitment. Execution of internal marketing initiatives by organizations should not be a preserve for managers in the retailing sector but should instead span across all managers in the general service industry. Since employees' organizational commitment is vital in enhancing overall employee performance, organizations are encouraged to embed sustainable internal marketing initiatives that can ensure employee satisfaction. Managers may foster internal marketing through internal communication, offering rewards commensurate with effort expended, training and involvement and participation of employees in decision-making processes, and enabling employees to speak their minds on aspects that affect their jobs.

Limitations and Directions for Further Study

The study was pursued in the context of small and medium retail enterprises in a developing country,

Zimbabwe. As such, the generalizability of results to a broader scope should be in light of the differences in organizational cultures and environments. This study can be replicated in the large retail and wholesale sectors. Similarly, replication and extension of the scope of the study can be done mainly in different work environments such as transport, telecommunications, and construction industries. It would also be thought-provoking to determine whether the internal marketing and organizational commitment variables used in this study would be appropriate in the large retail and wholesale sector and other industries other than retailing.

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